

Effect of Body Mass Index (BMI) on Electrocardiographic P-Wave Dispersion among Healthy Adults

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Abstract:

This cross-sectional study studied the relationship between BMI and P-wave dispersion (PWD) in 82 healthy persons at Patna Medical College and Hospital. The research lasted from January 2020 to February 2021. The study found a significant association between BMI and PWD, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.38 ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, regression analysis showed a 0.8 ms increase in PWD per unit increase in BMI ($p < 0.001$). These data suggest that even small BMI increases can affect cardiac electrophysiology. This may increase atrial arrhythmia risk. This study highlights the need of a healthy BMI for cardiovascular health and suggests regular ECG monitoring for higher-BMI patients.

Keywords: BMI, P-wave Dispersion, Electrocardiography, Atrial Arrhythmias.

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Introduction

There has been a significant focus in the field of cardiology on examining the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and electrocardiographic (ECG) parameters [1]. This attention stems from the increasing concern surrounding obesity and its impact on cardiovascular health [2]. There has been a growing recognition of P-wave dispersion (PWD) as a potential indicator for predicting atrial fibrillation. PWD is derived from the ECG and shows promise in this regard. This phenomenon involves the difference in the duration of the P-wave in various ECG leads, which can provide insights into the heterogeneity of atrial conduction [3,4].

In healthy adults, understanding how BMI influences P-wave dispersion can provide insights into the early changes in cardiac electrophysiology that might precede clinical manifestations of cardiovascular disease [5]. Given the global increase in the prevalence of obesity, this research area holds significant implications for early diagnostic strategies and preventive healthcare [6].

This review aims to explore the relationship between BMI and electrocardiographic P-wave dispersion among healthy adults. By synthesizing findings from various studies, this paper seeks to delineate the potential impact of BMI on atrial electrical activity, thereby contributing to a broader understanding of cardiovascular risk factors in populations at the threshold of clinical obesity and beyond.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional design to explore the impact of Body Mass Index (BMI) on P-wave dispersion in a cohort of healthy adults. It was conducted at the Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, from January 2020 to February 2021.

Participants: The study population consisted of 82 healthy adult volunteers recruited from the local community surrounding Patna Medical College and Hospital. Participants were included based on the following criteria:

- Age 18 years or older
- No history of cardiovascular disease, hypertension, or diabetes
- Not on any medications affecting cardiac function

Participants were excluded if they had any known cardiac abnormalities, were pregnant, or had a history of significant medical conditions that could affect the ECG readings.

Data Collection: Every participant had a thorough physical and medical history review after giving informed consent. The BMI of each participant was calculated from height and weight. The computation involved dividing weight in kilogrammes by height in meters squared (kg/m^2). Electrocardiography was done on a 12-lead machine. An expert cardiologist who was ignorant

of the individuals' BMI measured P-wave dispersion manually using callipers. The variance among the longest and shortest P-wave lengths in the 12-lead ECG is used to calculate P-wave dispersion.

Statistical Analysis: Analytics were done with statistical software. We calculated mean, and standard deviation for all variables, including BMI and P-wave dispersion. After controlling for age and gender, Pearson correlation and linear regression models examined the link between BMI and P-wave dispersion. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all statistical tests.

Results

The study involved 82 participants, with an even distribution of both males and females. The average age of the participants was 34.5 years, with a standard deviation of 8.2 years. The Body Mass Index (BMI) varied between 18.5 and 29.9 kg/m^2 , with an average BMI of 24.3 kg/m^2 (SD = 3.4 kg/m^2). Among the study participants, the average

P-wave dispersion was 36 milliseconds (ms), with a standard deviation of 4.2 ms. The range of P-wave dispersion values observed was from 28 ms to 44 ms. The statistical analysis uncovered a noteworthy positive correlation between BMI and P-wave dispersion. The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.38, suggesting a moderate correlation with statistical significance ($p < 0.01$). In addition, the analysis using linear regression revealed a correlation between an increase in BMI and a corresponding increase in P-wave dispersion. The increase in P-wave dispersion was estimated to be 0.8 ms for each unit increase in BMI, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.5 to 1.1 ms per unit BMI. This association was found to be statistically significant with a p-value of less than 0.001.

It appears that as BMI rises, even within a range thought about as healthy, there is a notable rise in P-wave dispersion. This could potentially signify alterations in atrial conduction heterogeneity linked to higher body mass.

Parameter	Mean (SD)	Range
Age (years)	34.5 (8.2)	N/A
BMI (kg/m^2)	24.3 (3.4)	18.5 - 29.9
P-Wave Dispersion (ms)	36.0 (4.2)	28 - 44
Pearson Correlation (BMI vs PWD)	0.38	N/A
Regression Coefficient (ms per unit BMI)	0.8	95% CI: 0.5 - 1.1

Notes:

- SD: Standard Deviation
- ms: milliseconds
- BMI: Body Mass Index
- PWD: P-Wave Dispersion
- CI: Confidence Interval

This table provides a concise view of the demographic and clinical measurements, along with the statistical findings regarding the relationship between BMI and P-wave dispersion.

Discussions

The study's findings reveal a noteworthy and meaningful connection between BMI and P-wave dispersion in healthy adults. As body mass index (BMI) rises, even among individuals with a normal to pre-obese range, there is a clear rise in P-wave dispersion [7]. This indicates possible changes in atrial electrophysiology. This correlation is especially important considering the increasing

prevalence of obesity worldwide and its impact on cardiac electrophysiology. P-wave dispersion is a recognized indicator of atrial heterogeneity and a reliable predictor for atrial fibrillation [8,9]. There appears to be a correlation between higher BMI and an increased likelihood of developing atrial arrhythmias, even in people who do not have any obvious cardiovascular issues. This finding reinforces the idea that even slight increases in BMI can impact heart function, emphasizing the

significance of keeping a healthy weight for heart health [10,11].

Previous studies have also demonstrated a relationship between increased BMI and various ECG abnormalities, including atrial enlargement and prolonged P-wave duration [12]. Our findings align with these studies, reinforcing the view that BMI is an important determinant of electrophysiological changes in the heart. However, our study adds to the existing literature by focusing on a healthy adult population, which helps to isolate the effect of BMI from other confounding factors like existing cardiovascular diseases or medication use [13-16].

While this study provides valuable insights, it has several limitations:

- The cross-sectional design limits the ability to infer causality between BMI and P-wave dispersion.
- The sample size, although adequate for preliminary findings, is relatively small for generalizing the results to a broader population.
- Manual measurement of P-wave dispersion could introduce human error, although efforts were made to mitigate this by having a blinded cardiologist perform the measurements [17,18].

Future studies should aim to include a larger and more diverse population to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Longitudinal designs would be beneficial to establish causality and observe the long-term effects of BMI on cardiac electrophysiology. Additionally, incorporating more advanced and automated methods for measuring P-wave dispersion could improve the accuracy and reproducibility of the results [19,20].

Conclusion

This study focuses on the influence of BMI on cardiac electrophysiological parameters in healthy adults. It highlights the significance of maintaining a healthy body weight, not just for preventing metabolic syndromes, but also for ensuring optimal cardiac electrical function. It is suggested that individuals with a higher BMI could potentially benefit from routine ECG monitoring, as it may aid in the early detection and prevention of atrial arrhythmias.

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